

T. S. Eliot's love for Indian philosophy and life values

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Abstract:

“Oh, East is East, and West is West, and never the twain shall meet” wrote Rudyard Kipling once. Ironically, T. S. Eliot's magnum opus *The Waste Land*, one of the canonical texts of the Western modernism, ends with a direct reference to an Eastern scripture—the Upanishad. The poem abounds in references to Indian philosophy, spirituality, religion, and history. The titles of two sections in the poem—“The Fire Sermon” and “What the Thunder Said”—bear direct allusions to Indian religions, namely Hinduism and Buddhism. Eliot places together two great masters of asceticism—Lord Buddha and Saint Augustine—from the East and the West. The ultimate solution to the social ills, spiritual banality, religious bankruptcy, degradation of emotions, and predicament of human virtues in the modern Western world is found in the Indian principles of Datta (Charity), Dayadhvam (Compassion), and Damyata (Restraint). The present paper analyzes the influence of the Indian spiritual and philosophical traditions in *The Waste Land* and Eliot's deep and consistent love for the Indian philosophy and life values.

Keywords: T. S. Eliot, Upanishad, Buddhism, Hinduism, Vedas, *The Waste Land*

Introduction:

One among the many western scholars, who was greatly influenced by Indian philosophy, T.S. Eliot becomes a key factor in his poem, the magnum opus, *The Waste Land*. He had a dominant poetic voice in the 1920s. Eliot used an essential, allusive and elliptical technique to put across the view that modern western urban civilisation was sterile and unsatisfying. He avoided personal emotion in contrast to the more romantic effusions of the Georgian poets. His distaste for romanticism, a desire to treat the poem in isolation from the poet and the cult of traditional classical values went hand in hand with a dislike of the modern world. And here he came to love the Indian way of living and thinking.

The hoary Indian wisdom has attracted many intellectuals in the West. With the growth of Indology in England and Germany, Europe turned to the East. During the mid-nineteenth century, Emerson, Thoreau, and Whitman had begun publishing poems, essays and books

containing oriental colourings. In those days, Harvard had become a famous centre for oriental studies. T.S. Eliot among others, studied there from 1906 to 1914. In those days, he came in contact with his learned Gurus like Charles R. Lanman and James H. Woods, who themselves were busy in reading and anthologizing books related to Hinduism. T.S. Eliot presented the credentials of a wide range of poetic sensibility by incorporating in his poetry not only the best of European culture and American mind but also of Indian thought and tradition.

Vedas and Upanishads: In his poetry, references abound to show that he had knowledge of the Vedas, the Upanishads, the Bhagavadgita and Patanjali's Yoga-Sutras. He was well versed in Buddhistic lore and literature too. His poem *The Wasteland* is both vedic in origin and Upanishadic in content.

In 1922, a literary landmark was born in the field of modern poetry. T.S. Eliot's *The Waste Land* first appeared in *The Dial* after winning the same magazine's Poetry award. Instantly, it found success, taking the world of literature by storm. In 1948, it won him the Nobel prize in literature.

Only nine years before the *Waste Land* was first published, Rabindranath Tagore had won the Nobel prize for literature. At the onset, we may not see an obvious correlation between these two monumental works written in completely different parts of the world. But when we look closer, many allusions and inspirations are revealed in Eliot's work that point to major influences from India and Indian spirituality.

The poem for which Eliot is best known is his 1922 modernist masterpiece *The Waste Land*. There, Eliot captured the mood of the Western world following the horrors of World War I and the tedium of industrialized urban society. *The Waste Land*, however, makes no effort to isolate horror and boredom to a specific geographical, political, or historical context. Through the use of imagery, allusion, and rhythm which transcends any single context and which draws upon a number of cultural traditions, Eliot extrapolates from contemporary events to the universal human condition, highlighting a certain uneasiness with self and other within it.

Patanjali and Yoga Shastra: The great Hindu mystic, Patanjali also finds birth in Eliot's poetry. Yoga-Sutras, had truly left the poet in a state of enlightened mystification. The end of all yoga is liberation (moksha) which implies the annihilation of the individual and the ultimate immersion into the divine soul. The self mortifications and austerities of Patanjali's Yoga provided Eliot with "not only the answer to a religious need, but also the matter for a poetry of contemplation which should be both intense and dramatic". The practice of Yoga necessitates the absentation from movement, both physical and mental Patanjali's Eight fold path assists the practitioner to

achieve this salutary objective. The eight dimensions of the path are abstention (yama), observance (niyama), Posture (asana), breath control (Pranayama), sense withdrawal (pratyahara), concentration (dhyana), contemplation (dharana), and profound meditation (Samadhi). These eight fold path are necessary to achieve the objective.

Buddhism: Buddhism also exercised a firm hold on the poet. Eliot regarded the Buddha as an ideal representative of the Eastern asceticism. In one place, Eliot observed that “some of the early Buddhist scriptures affected me as parts of the old Testament do”. The very title of the third section of *The Wasteland* is directly drawn from Buddhism. When this poem was being written Eliot seriously thought of becoming a Buddhist. The Buddhistic doctrine of death-wish and Nirvana; that is the state of existence in which man is totally freed from all sense-perceptions.

In the entire arena of the World Literature, no other philosophical epic has drawn the attention of the readers, irrespective of clan and creed, time and place as the *Bhagavadgita*; it is because the mankind in its totality had derived from it that content that shows them the right path. Whenever man finds himself in a state of indecision and spiritual bewilderment in determining the right course of action; the *Bhagavadgita* inspires a man to follow the path of right and disinterested action with knowledge of a desireless devotion to the Almighty. For Eliot, the *Gita* was by far the most important Indic text he read and the one that most deeply and extensively inspired his poetry. In *The Criterion*, Eliot praises Arjuna's balance of mind: That balance of mind which a few highly civilized individuals, such as Arjuna the hero of the *Bhagavadgita*, can maintain in action. The *Gita* aims at providing the valuable instructions like right and disinterested action and detachment. The poems and plays of T.S. Eliot in their pattern of ideas exhibit the basic concepts of the *Bhagavadgita*. His poem “*To The Indians who Died in Africa*” refers to the Hindu concept of Karma (action) as propounded in the *Bhagavadgita* which was so dear to the poet that he called it “the next greatest philosophical poem to the *Divine comedy* with in my experience”. The poem under review appeared in the commemorative volume entitled *Queens Mary's Book for India* which is addressed to Indians who laid down their lives while fighting far away from their motherland during the second world war. In these Indians Eliot discovered an excellent objective correlative of ‘selfless action’ performed in the spirit of dispassion and detachment. The content of this poem is quite identical to that of the *Gita* and in both the burden is on doing one's duty without any desire for ‘the fruit of action’. The selfless action according to the *Gita* is the highest and easiest kind of Yoga: And do not think of the fruit of action. The desire of getting ‘the fruit of action’ binds the soul to the body, whereas the duty done in perfect detachment liberates it for good and the end of Yoga is liberation from the human bondage. *Four Quartets* is a series of four poems that appeared from time to time. These poems

are named after different proper places. The most explicit note of Hinduism strikes us in “The Dry Salvages”. In the second movement of the poem occurs: Time the destroyer is timethe preserver.¹⁹It verily recounts the Hindu concept of time in relation to timelessness. T.S. Eliot has shown an inclination to Indian Literature and poetry, to Indian asceticism and metaphysics and to Indian thought and religion. T.S. Eliot himself has confessed that his poetry “shows the influence of Indian thought and sensibility” which is reflected in his works.

Oriental Influences:

In her essay titled T. S. Eliot’s *The Waste Land: A Perspective on Indian Thoughts*, Dr Rajani Sharma points out “the Indian sensibility with its Christian Intent” that makes this poem unique.

To understand the alchemical congruence of the East and the West that went into this globally resounding poem, one has to understand the context of the times it was written in and that of the influences over the poet.

The title reflects the utter barrenness of the human condition that caused a spiritual fog in the post-World War world. Eliot reckoned that such degradation borne of lust, greed and anger would lead to a state of annihilation. So what was the solution?

In the mid-nineteenth century, Indian thought became a subject of interest to many western writers. When Eliot arrived at Harvard, it became a famous center for Oriental studies. His mentors included Irving Babbit and George Santayana, who were instrumental in his developing an interest in Indian scripture and philosophy. He went on to enroll in Indic courses where he started studying Pali and Sanskrit as part of his interest in Hinduism and Buddhism.

Eliot said, “Long ago I studied the ancient Indian languages, and while I was chiefly interested at that time in philosophy, I read a little poetry too, and I know that my poetry shows the influence of Indian thought.”

The Waste Land: A Universal Solution

Through these comprehensive influences, Eliot concurred that the conundrum of the mechanical spiritual death could not be solved only by the West, and needed a universal solution.

It is no surprise then that the headings for two of the five sections of the poem are derived from Indian sources, alongside the symbolism of the Grail Legend and the Fisher King. In a true modernist style, the poem features abrupt changes of speakers, place and time, portraying the dissonance that is emblematic of its subject matter. It also interweaves scenes from contemporary British life into the labyrinth of these myths and higher thoughts.

The Five sections

The first section, called *The Burial of the Dead*, talks about the rejuvenation of modern humanity with the drop of rainwater. The poem says:

April is the cruelest month, breeding

Lilacs out of the dead land, mixing

Memory and desire, stirring

Dull roots with spring rain.

Drawn from the Buddhist text, *Dhammapada*, this thought can be traced back to Gautam Buddha, who suggests growing a Bodhi tree in his heart by becoming spiritually aware of his existence.

The next section, *A Game of Chess*, is a contemporary exploration of the degradation of marriage and sex in modern society.

The third section, called, *The Fire Sermon*, is derived directly from a sermon of Lord Buddha. This section focuses on fighting temptations on the path and overcoming desire to lead to nirvana. Here, Eliot draws not only from Buddha's idea of ascetism, but also from St. Augustine.

The next section titled, *Death by Fire*, builds on the idea of the fire sermon. Here, the self is transformed from a gross being into an enlightened being. The Vedic concept of *tapa* is touched upon here.

In his essay called *The Upanishad in the Wasteland*, G. Nageshwara Rao writes, "Drought throughout Eliot's poetry is metaphor for despair, doubt and need for spiritual certainty. Just as water is taught by thirst, the need for nourishing faith is taught by a restless state of doubt in which one can neither stand or lie nor sit."

The last section, *The Word of the Thunder*, is completely based on the Upanishads. The *Brihadaranyaka Upanishad* alludes to Prajapathi, the creator, talking to his three offsprings—Devas, Demons and Men: reiterating the cardinal virtues of *Damyata* (Restraint), *Datta* (Charity) and *Dayadhvam* (Compassion). The voice of the thunder ends on a positive note when the poem ends with the command, "Shantih, Shantih, Shantih." Eliot wishes peace upon all, even the wastelanders who are gripped by fear.

In a letter to Bertrand Russell, Eliot described the last section as, "not only the best part but the part that justifies the whole." This statement is not only revealing but extremely powerful

because it sums up the immense power of the Vedas and Upanishads that form the structural matrix of the poem. While this is not an Indian poem per se, its strong message of the power of Indian philosophy still resonates a hundred years on. And perhaps will, for many more centuries.

TS Eliot once wrote that the great philosophers of India "make most of the great European philosophers look like schoolboys" and although he's more often remembered as an establishment figure - somewhat conservative and deeply Christian - Eliot also wrote about and studied Indian philosophy, language and culture. He incorporated it into his most famous poems and even considered becoming a Buddhist.

We see that many Indian writers became intrigued at school by Eliot's poem *The Waste Land*, which ends with the Sanskrit mantra 'shantih, shantih, shantih'.

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